

To study troposphere–stratosphere trace gases (Ozone and Water vapour) exchange in UTLS region over tropical and subtropical regions

Tsehaye Negash^{a,b,*}, U.Prakash Raju^{a,*}

^aCollege of Science, Department of Physics, Washera Geospace and Radar Science Research Laboratory(WaGRL), Bahir Dar University, P.O.Box 79, Ethiopia

^bCollege of Natural and Computational Science, Department of Physics, Injibar University, P.O.Box 40, Ethiopia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ozone
Water Vapour
Aura MLS
Mixing Ratio
UTLS
Season
Tropopause

ABSTRACT

Water vapor and ozone are crucial trace gases in the atmosphere, playing a vital role in climate change within the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS). Understanding their behavior is particularly important for studying atmospheric dynamics and predicting tropical cyclones. In this study, we analyzed the vertical profiles of ozone and water vapor variation in the UTLS of both tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt regions using AURA/MLS satellite data. Our analysis focused on data from the AURA/MLS satellites spanning from January 2006 to December 2020, with an emphasis on the tropical and subtropical regions. Overall, except summer in Ethiopia, the ozone distribution in the UTLS remains relatively stable. In Egypt, ozone levels remain stable during autumn. However, during winter, tropospheric ozone levels in tropical Egypt are generally lower compared to summer and autumn. The transport of ozone from the stratosphere to the troposphere is controlled by the tropical CPT_h, while the transport of water vapor across the tropopause is controlled by the tropical CPT_t. The annual mean ozone volume mixing ratio (OVMR) variability in subtropical Egypt ranges from 6 to 9 ppmv at UTLS, within the pressure interval of 50 to 0.001 hPa. In tropical Ethiopia, the variability ranges from 6 to 10 ppmv within the pressure range of 50 to 0.001 hPa. The annual variability of mean WVMR in tropical Ethiopia shows peak values ranging from 400 to 600 ppmv at UTLS, between the pressure levels of 200 to 300 hPa, typically occurring in May, June, July, and August. In contrast, subtropical Egypt experiences peak WVMR values of 100 to 200 ppmv at UTLS, within the pressure range of 200 to 300 hPa, usually around March to June. Our study reveals that Egypt has a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to Ethiopia. In the tropical Ethiopia region, we observe SAO in the WVMR, while AO is observed in the OVMR. On the other hand, in subtropical Egypt, TAO is observed in the WVMR, and AO is observed in the OMR. Over a period of 15 years, the maximum mass flux of ozone crossing the tropopause is 5 kg/s (equivalent to 6.57×10^5 kg of ozone) in Egypt and 3.4 kg/s (equivalent to 4.47×10^5 kg of ozone) in Ethiopia. In terms of water vapor, the maximum mass flux crossing the tropopause is 68 kg/s (equivalent to 8.94×10^6 kg of water vapor) in tropical Ethiopia and 30 kg/s (equivalent to 3.94×10^6 kg of water vapor) in subtropical Egypt. Our study reveals that Egypt experiences a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to Ethiopia. Conversely, Ethiopia experiences a higher water vapor mass flux in the tropopause compared to Egypt.

1. Introduction

In the Earth's atmosphere, upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) is an important region, where the interactions of different processes take place. These include dynamical, radiative and chemical processes together with the exchange of air mass and key minor constituents such as water vapor, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and ozone across the tropopause. This two-way transport of air masses and minor constituents between the troposphere and the stratosphere is generally known as stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE) (Holton et al., 1995). These exchange processes play a crucial role in controlling the Earth's radiation budget and are directly linked to the characteristics of

*Corresponding authors :-Tsehaye Negash and U.Prakash Raju

✉ tsehaybla89@gmail.com (T. Negash); lidarraju@gmail.com (U.Prakash Raju)

ORCID(s): 0000-0003-1949-7574 (U.Prakash Raju)

the UTLS region (Fueglistaler et al., 2009). According to Holton et al. (1995), the distinction between troposphere and stratosphere is important and useful because of two primary reasons. Firstly, due to the difference in vertical transport time scales in the troposphere and stratosphere. In the troposphere vertical motions can occur on time scales as short as few hours to days; few hours via moist convection in the tropics and few days via baroclinic eddy motions in middle latitudes. However, in the lower stratosphere, due to the increased static stability, vertical motions occurs on time scales of several months to year (Brasseur and Solomon, 2005). Moreover, the stratosphere is highly stratified and poorly mixed, the chemical constituents ejected into this layer from troposphere probably will have an increased life-time. Secondly due to the difference in chemical composition between them, the tropospheric air is clearly distinct from the stratosphere. The inhibition of vertical mixing by the strong inversion layer, the stratosphere, results in concentration gradients in the several atmospheric constituents across the tropopause. The tropospheric air is normally considered as moist and ozone-poor whereas stratospheric air is extremely dry and ozone-rich. The water vapour distribution in the air is largely influenced by the air (atmospheric) temperature as explained by Clausius-Clapeyron relation. This relation results in a rapid decrease in water vapour concentration with altitude in troposphere as temperature decreases. A noticeable increase in ozone concentration is also observed just above the tropopause. A basic assumption is that the troposphere is in convective-radiative equilibrium. In the troposphere, interaction among radiative transfer, convection and large-scale dynamics regulate the vertical temperature structure. In the troposphere there is a net radiative cooling due to GHGs. However the stratosphere is close to radiative equilibrium. In the stratosphere, cooling due to the emission of longwave radiation by H_2O and O_3 nearly balances the radiative heating due to the absorption of solar UV radiation by O_3 . Further, the relative abundance of these radiatively active minor constituents (O_3 and H_2O) in the UTLS region plays a significant role in determining the clear sky level of zero net radiative heating, which occurs at ~ 17 km in the tropics and ~ 15 in the subtropics (Gettelman et al., 2010; Fueglistaler et al., 2009). It is assumed that above this level, air parcel always experiences a net radiative heating and thus more chances to ascent slowly into the stratosphere. Owing to its distinguished characteristics in terms of the chemical composition and dynamics, studies on the UTLS region is still a focus of great interest in the scientific community dealing with exchange processes and atmospheric chemistry.

The transport of air from the stratosphere to the troposphere and vice versa plays an important role in the dynamics and composition of the atmosphere. The extreme dryness of the stratosphere, for example, is a result of the transport from the troposphere to the stratosphere in the tropics, where the air is strongly dried when it passes the very cold tropopause. Stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE) is also important for the human impact on the atmosphere. CFCs which cause enhanced chemical ozone destruction in the stratosphere, are released at the earth's surface due to human activities and are transported into the stratosphere in the tropics. From here the CFCs are transported toward the poles where the ozone depletion takes place. (this is to be limitation study) Despite extensive research on STE, there are still large

uncertainties in several important qualitative and quantitative aspects of STE. Recently, [Butchart and Scaife \(2001\)](#) predicted an increase of the air-mass exchange between the troposphere and the stratosphere with 3% per decade due to enhanced greenhouse gas concentrations. In order to investigate the impact of enhanced greenhouse gas concentrations on STE, it is important to simulate the involved transport processes correctly. The transport of air from the troposphere to the stratosphere occurs primarily through the cold tropical tropopause regions over the tropics. Due to this reason, dehydration of stratospheric air is strongly coupled to variability of tropical tropopause temperatures ([Brewer, 1949](#); [Fueglistaler et al., 2009](#)). In the Hadley cell air rises in the tropics from the surface to upper troposphere. Above the Hadley cell further ascent is caused by the BDC in the stratosphere. When air passing through the cold regions of the tropical tropopause, it is freeze-dried and retains only the saturation mixing ratio corresponding to the low temperatures. Hence the signal of water vapour mixing ratio corresponding to the tropopause temperature is maintained by the air parcel as it ascends through the stratosphere. [Mote et al. \(1996\)](#) have made a classical study, which provided evidence for the connection between annual variation of tropical tropopause temperature and stratospheric water vapour mixing ratio. From the satellite measurement of water vapour mixing ratio, [Mote et al. \(1996\)](#) presented the evidence for the slow ascent in the stratosphere. The Stratosphere–Troposphere Exchange (STE) is critically important for understanding the interactive chemical–dynamical–radiative process of the atmosphere. The exchange can introduce the tropospheric source gases (water vapor) into the stratosphere and bring ozone-rich air down into the troposphere. The resultant redistribution of the chemical composition in both the troposphere and the stratosphere has a substantial impact on the radiative budget that causes global climate change, as well as the chemical and dynamical characteristics of the atmosphere ([Holton et al., 1995](#)). The predictions of future radiative forcing depend on accurate simulations of the upper tropospheric and lower stratospheric chemical concentrations, and hence on accurate simulations of the cross-tropopause transport of air mass and trace gases ([Collins et al., 2003](#)). Therefore, it is necessary to understand the dynamical processes across the Cold Point Tropopause (~ 17 km, ~ 100 hPa in the tropics and ~ 14 km, ~ 150 hPa in the subtropics) troposphere stratosphere to estimate the amount of their exchange ([Fueglistaler et al., 2009](#)). It is generally accepted that most air enters the stratosphere in the tropics [Brewer \(1949\)](#); [Dobson \(1956\)](#) by a combination of rapid vertical motion in convection ([Corti et al., 2008](#)) and slow diabatic ascent ([Holton and Gettelman, 2001](#)). Some studies have observed the injection of tropospheric air into the lower stratosphere near the tropopause based on satellite data, aircraft measurements and in situ observations ([Richard et al., 2001](#); [Romps and Kuang, 2009](#)), which can be revealed by the ozone and water concentration.

The distribution of water vapor (WV) in the atmosphere is concentrated mainly below 500 hPa. Above the middle troposphere, including the upper troposphere and the lower stratosphere (UTLS) at 8~20 km, the water vapor mixing ratio (WVMR) is 2~4 times lower than in the lower troposphere. The radiation force produced by the distribution and transformation of WV in UTLS region can change the energy balance of the earth-atmosphere system, and it can have

a vital impact on global climate change (Held and Soden, 2000), due to WV is a greenhouse gases which influence on the radiation balance caused by twice that of carbon dioxide in the tropical troposphere (Sinha and Harries, 1995) on the other hand the refrigeration effect caused by increasing WV and ozone fluctuation is considerable (de F. Forster and Shine, 1999) And WV is the OH radical of photochemical reaction in the stratosphere, and an influence on the distribution and variation of ozone in the stratosphere (Oltmans and Hofmann, 1995). Methane oxidation process and upward transportation from the troposphere are the two dominating factors determining how much WV is in the stratosphere (Kremser et al., 2008; Hurst et al., 2014; Lambert et al., 2007; Cooper et al., 2005). In addition, the variation of WV in the UTLS is affected by tropopause temperature and BD circulation (SHI et al., 2009). Water vapor and ozone are the two primary greenhouse gases (GHGs) that have a significant impact on the energy-radiation balance in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) region. The quantity of water vapor injected into the stratosphere is largely determined by the temperature of the tropical tropopause. Even minor changes in stratospheric water vapor can have a significant influence on both stratospheric chemistry and the global radiation balance (Holton et al., 1995; de F. Forster and Shine, 1999). Recent research utilizing the characteristics of the tropical tropopause has revealed a widening of the tropical belt, which is associated with climate change (Seidel et al., 2008; Seidel and Randel, 2006; Birner, 2010). This widening of the tropical belt results in an increased area of upwelling, which, in combination with its strength, can lead to a greater transport of water vapor into the stratosphere. The ongoing research focuses on determining the frequency and locations of stratospheric intrusions reaching the planetary boundary layer. Additionally, the extent to which stratospheric intrusions contribute to surface ozone and water levels is also being investigated. Notable studies in this field include those conducted by Davies and Schuepbach (1994); Stohl et al. (2000); Vingarzan (2004); Trickl et al. (2010); Cristofanelli et al. (2010); Lefohn et al. (2012); Kuang et al. (2012); Lin et al. (2012). The present study presents a comprehensive analysis of the tropical and subtropical climatology of Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange (STE) from 2006 to 2020. This analysis is based on an improved version of the Lagrangian method originally proposed by Wernli and Bourqui (2002) , combined with data from the state-of-the-art Micro wave Limb sounder (MLS). By utilizing this methodology, we are able to investigate the pathways of transport between the stratosphere and the troposphere (STT) as well as between the troposphere and the stratosphere (TST). Stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE) events play a key role in controlling the ozone and water vapor budgets of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) region. The exchange of mass across the tropopause is bidirectional, with a return flow transporting tropospheric air into the lowermost stratosphere (Danielsen, 1968; Hoor et al., 2002). It occurs via a variety of processes on different scales which include both Troposphere to Stratosphere Transport (TST) (Zahn et al., 2000; Hoor et al., 2002) and Stratosphere to Troposphere Transport (STT) (Shapiro, 1980; Danielsen, 1968) events. the transport of tropospheric air into the stratosphere is irreversible (Hintsa et al., 1998). Conversely, the STT events happen everywhere but dominate in the midlatitudes. The depletion of stratospheric ozone over antartica

is mainly due to stratospheric chlorine and temperature in the Antarctica vortex (Strahan and Douglass, 2018). A major effect of ozone loss is on tropospheric temperature, circulation, precipitation, ocean, and ecosystem (Gillett and Thompson, 2003; Baldwin et al., 2007; Kuttippurath and Nair, 2017). Stratospheric ozone loss over the tropical region can also be due to stratospheric intrusions into the troposphere, which increases the tropospheric ozone (Das et al., 2016). However, O₃, being a greenhouse gas, has an important role in the climate forcing due to its oxidizing nature in the troposphere (Forster et al., 2007; Pan et al., 2014; Akritidis et al., 2019). Water vapor and ozone are measured in situ by balloon, ozonsonde and aircraft based instruments, and remotely by satellite and ground based sensors. Unfortunately, it is difficult to obtain accurate, pressure resolved global scale measurements of water vapor and ozone in the upper troposphere lower stratosphere (UTLS). This work is first of its kind to observe trace gases of water vapor and ozone analysis from tropics and subtropics using AURA/MLS satellite observations over a period of 2006 to 2020. The methodology and data availability are covered in section 2. Section 3 describes the outcome and the discussion. Part 4 describes the summary and conclusion.

2. Data and the Analysis Methods

2.1. AURA MLS Satellite

The Aura satellite was launched on 15 July 2004 and placed into a near-polar Earth orbit at ~705km with an inclination of 98° and an ascending node at 13:45h. It makes about 14 orbits per day. The MLS instrument onboard Aura uses the microwave limb sounding technique to measure chemical constituents and dynamical tracers between the upper troposphere and the lower mesosphere (Waters et al., 2006). It provides dense spatial coverage with 3500 profiles daily between 82° N and 82° S. The horizontal grid of the on-board MLS instrument is every 1.5° or about 165 km along the track. The instrument can obtain atmospheric composition data including WV, carbon monoxide, and ozone using microwave detection technology. Version 6.2 of Level 2 water vapor and Ozone data used in this study was derived from the 190 GHz channel, and it is significantly better than the V5.2 or V4.2 or V3.3 or V2.2 (Livesey et al., 2011; Hurst et al., 2014; Froidevaux et al., 2008) data. The MLS observation data are reliable at several different heights, and an effective vertical range from 316 to 0.002 hPa is recommended (Hurst et al., 2014; Read et al., 2007). The WV vertical resolution is 2.5 km from 316 to 215 hPa and degrades to 3 km from 100 to 1 hPa and Ozone vertical resolution is ~3 km from 256 to 0.01 hPa in the upper troposphere and the stratosphere. MLS measures vertical profiles at 3500 locations in the world every 24 hours (Froidevaux et al., 2006; Ziemke et al., 2011; Jiang et al., 2010). Since this study focused on the climatological characteristics of WV and Ozone at the seasonal scale over the tropical and subtropical region in the Northern hemisphere. The seasons were defined based on the northern hemisphere: spring (March, April, and May-MAM), summer (June, July, and August-JJA), autumn (September, October, and November-SON), and winter (December, 2nd January, and 2nd February-DJF). In order to

facilitate mapping and analysis, the WVMR data were taken with a resolution of $0.5^0 \times 0.5^0$ on a latitude-longitude grid. Most of the ozonesondes have burst altitudes near 10 hPa hence MLS ozone profiles are evaluated from surface to 10 hPa. Although suitable collocation criteria have been defined for a fair comparison, the different vertical resolutions of the two datasets (ozonesonde ~ 100 m and 1 – 5 km in MLS) still make the meaningful comparison difficult (Maddy and Barnett, 2008). The Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (Waters, 1993; Waters et al., 2006), an advanced successor to the MLS instrument on the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS), is a limb sounding instrument which measures thermal emission at millimeter and submillimeter wavelengths using seven radiometers to cover five broad spectral regions. The radiometric and spectral performance of the MLS instrument is covered in detail by Jarnot et al. (2006) for the GHz radiometers and by Pickett (2006) for the THz radiometer. The standard H_2O and O_3 products are retrieved from the radiances measured by the radiometers centered near 190 GHz (R_2), and 640 GHz (R_4), respectively. The MLS line of sight is in the forward direction of the Aura spacecraft flight track. The Earth's limb is scanned from the surface to 90 km every 26.6 s giving 240 scans per orbit spaced at 1.5^0 intervals (165 km) with a total of ~ 3500 vertical profiles per day and a nearly global latitude coverage from 82^0S to 82^0N . The viewing geometry of the MLS instrument allows the innovative use of a two-dimensional approach to the retrieval problem since the limb observations from successive scans overlap significantly which means that effects of line-of-sight gradients can be taken into account (Livesey and Read, 2000). For the assimilation experiment, MLS data are selected according to the precision and quality flags recommended in the MLS Version6.2 Leve2 data quality and description document (<http://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/data/v6-2dataqualitydocument.pdf>).

2.2. Methodology

Tracer–Based Calculation: The mass flux can be estimated by multiplying the concentration of a tracer (in this case ozone and water vapor) that indicates stratospheric or tropospheric air by the cross-tropopause. To calculate the mass flux across a surface, we count the number of trajectories that cross the tropopause. The general formula for mass flux of the tracer is:

$$F_{flux} = \rho v A \quad (1)$$

Where, F_{flux} is the mass flux of Ozone and Water vapor, ρ is the density of the gas (density of ozone and water vapor) in the tropopause, v is the velocity of Ozone and Water vapor during the tropopause crossing, and A is the cross sectional area of Ozone and Water vapor in the tropopause variation. The stratosphere to the troposphere (STT) density of ozone and Troposphere to the stratosphere (TST) density of water are calculated as:

$$\rho_{O_3} = 1.66 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_{H_2O} = 0.62 \frac{P}{T} C \quad (3)$$

Where, P is tropopause pressure (in our study the tropopause pressure of tropical (Ethiopia) is 100 hPa and tropopause pressure of subtropical (Egypt) is 150 hPa), T is tropopause temperature, and C is concentration or mixing ratio of Ozone or water vapor we get from Aura/MLS satellite. Apart from the tropopause altitude oscillation, the tropopause temperature oscillation plays a significant role in the transport of water vapour from the troposphere to the lower stratosphere (Brewer 1949). The holding capacities of water vapour in the air and hence the saturation mixing ratio of air is a strong function of air temperature (Clausius-Clapeyron relation). The Saturation Mixing Ratio (SMR) with respect to ice is estimated using the following equation (Bolton,1980; Murphy and Koop 2005)

$$SMR = 0.623 \left(\frac{e_{si}}{P - e_{si}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where, SMR is saturation mixing ratio, P is pressure in hPa, and e_{si} is saturation vapor pressure in hPa is given by

$$e_{si} = \exp\left(9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T} + 3.53068 \ln(T) - 0.00728332T\right) \quad (5)$$

T is the tropopause temperature in Kelvin and P is the pressure in hPa (Pressure near the tropopause in tropical region is 100 hPa and subtropical region is 150 hPa).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Long - term monthly and annual mean UTLS water vapor and ozone variation in tropical (Ethiopia) and subtropical (Egypt) region

This section utilizes 15 years (2006–2020) of water vapor (316 - 0.001 hPa) and ozone (261 - 0.001 hPa) data from the MLS satellite in the pressure range known as the upper troposphere lower stratosphere (UTLS). The contour shown in Figure 1 (a - b) illustrates the monthly and annual mean water profiles in the tropical regions, specifically in the pressure range of 300 to 0.001 hPa. In Figure 1 (c), the lower left panels display the contours of monthly mean ozone variations observed by MLS. Additionally, the right lower panel of Figure 1 (d) showcases the annual mean ozone variations observed by MLS over tropical stations. The monthly mean water vapor volume mixing ratio (WVMR) below 200 hPa is relatively low, ranging from about 100–200 ppmv. However, above 200 hPa, it increases from 600 to 1000 ppmv. Figure 1 (b) demonstrates the annual mean WVMR variability, with peak values in the range of 400-600 ppmv at UTLS (200-300 hPa) during May-June-July-August. At pressures below 200 hPa, the annual mean WVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 50 to 100 ppmv. Moreover, the UTLS (200-300 hPa) exhibits the highest

observed SAO values, with a peak of 490 ppmv in May and 520 ppmv in August. In Figure 1 (d), the annual mean ozone volume mixing ratio (OVMR) variability is shown, with peak values in the range of 6-10 ppmv at UTLS (0.001-50 hPa) throughout the year. At pressures above 50 hPa, the annual mean OVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 1 to 4 ppmv. Additionally, an annual oscillation (AO) is observed in the UTLS around July/August. Our findings are in good agreement with prior research (Dessler et al., 2013; Jeffery et al., 2022; Selkirk et al., 2010).

Figure 2 (a - d) depicts similar analyses of the monthly mean and annual mean water vapor and ozone profiles for the subtropical Egypt region. The contours in the Figure 2 represent the pressure range of water vapor (316 - 0.001 hPa) and ozone (261 - 0.001 hPa). The left vertical panels of Figure 2 (a & c) show the contours of the monthly mean water vapor (a) and ozone (c) variations based on MLS observations. On the other hand, the right panel of Figure 2 (b & d) displays the displacements of the annual mean water vapor (b) and ozone (d) variations from MLS observations over the subtropical Egypt region. The monthly mean WVMR below 200 hPa is fairly low, ranging from about 5–100 ppmv. However, above 200 hPa, the WVMR increases from 200 to 350 ppmv. Figure 2 (b) illustrates the variability of the annual mean WVMR with peak values ranging from 100 to 200 ppmv at UTLS (200 - 300 hPa) around March to June. At pressures below 200 hPa, the annual mean WVMR concentrations are very low, ranging from 10 to 100 ppmv. Additionally, the TAO (Triannual oscillation) was observed to have a peak value of 190 ppmv in March, 200 ppmv in Jun, and 195 in september at the UTLS (200 - 300 hPa) as shown in Figure 2 (b). Figure 2 (d) demonstrates the annual mean OVMR variability, with peak OVMR values ranging from 6 - 9 ppmv at UTLS (50 - 0.001 hPa) through out the year. At pressures above 50 hPa, the annual mean OVMR concentrations are very low, with variability ranging from 1 to 5 ppmv.

3.2. The temporal and spatial distribution (Latitudinal variation) of water vapor and ozone in tropical (Ethiopia) and subtropical (Egypt) region

The distribution of water vapor and ozone in tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt reflects the complex dynamics of atmospheric processes influenced by geography, climate, and seasonality. For this study, we focused on the pressure intervals of 326 to 0.001 hPa for water vapor and 261 to 0.001 hPa for ozone in the latitudinal intervals of 0 - 15° N for tropical Ethiopia and 22 - 35° N for subtropical Egypt, specifically in the UTLS region. Figure 3 illustrates the spatial distribution of water vapor (WV) and ozone in the UTLS region over the tropical and subtropical regions from 2006 to 2020. In Figure 3 (a), we observe that the highest concentration of WV, ranging from 400 to 500 ppmv, is found in the latitudinal interval 0 - 12° N within the pressure range of 356 - 250 hPa. This is primarily due to the strong monsoonal flows bringing moisture from the Indian ocean and the Atlantic ocean. Additionally, this period coincides with enhanced convective activity, which further increases water vapor levels. Conversely, the minimum value of WV, ranging from 50 to 200 ppmv, is observed below 200 hPa. This decrease in WV concentration can be

attributed to a transition from the southwestern to the northeastern region. In Figure 3 (b), the highest concentration of WV, ranging from 150 to 200 ppmv, is found in the latitudinal interval of 22 - 28° N within the pressure range of 356 - 250 hPa. Egypt has a predominantly dry climate, with a brief rainy season occurring from November to April. During these cooler months, water vapor levels reach their peak, although they still remain relatively low due to limited rainfall. The minimum value of WV is observed to be below 200 hPa, ranging between 50–100 ppmv. According to Figure 3 (c), the highest ozone levels, between 6–8.8 ppmv, can be found in the latitudinal interval of 0 - 20° N and within the pressure interval of 50–0.001 hPa. These elevated ozone levels are typically found in areas with significant agricultural activities and biomass burning. on the otherhand, the minimum value of ozone is observed above 50 hPa, ranging between 1-4 ppmv, as forested highlands may have lower ozone concentrations due to less human induced activity. Referring to Figure 3 (d), the highest ozone value is between 6–7.8 ppmv in the latitudinal interval of 22 - 35° N and within the pressure interval of 50 - 0.001 hPa. These higher levels of ozone in Egypt can be attributed to increased photochemical reactions driven by higher temperatures and intense sunlight. Urban and industrial areas, such as Cairo, experience elevated ground level ozone concentrations due to pollution and vehicular emissions. The minimum value of ozone is also observed above 50 hPa, ranging between 1-5 ppmv. This lower value of ozone is a result of reduced sunlight and lower temperatures.

The global distribution of water vapor and ozone in the vertical cross section (latitude vs pressure) across the UTLS region, as described by MLS measurement, is shown in Figure 4. In Figure 4 (a), it can be observed that the maximum WV distribution occurs between 20S - 20° N in the pressure range of 356–200 hPa. This concentration is more pronounced near the equator (between 20° S and 20° N) due to higher temperatures and increased evaporation rates. The pressure range of 356-200 hPa corresponds to altitudes in the middle to upper troposphere, where much of the Earth's weather and moisture dynamics take place. On the otherhand, the minimum water vapor distribution is observed between 80S - 20° S and 20S - 80° N in the pressure range of 200–0.001 hPa. This range represents very high altitudes, ranging from the upper troposphere (around 200 hPa) to the lower stratosphere and beyond (down to 0.001 hPa, near the mesosphere). The reduced WV in these regions can be attributed to Colder Temperatures (At higher latitudes and altitudes, temperatures are significantly lower, reducing the air's moisture holding capacity), Stratospheric Dynamics (limited vertical mixing with the moist troposphere in the stratosphere and mesosphere), and polar regions, and Polar Regions (80°S and 80°N) where reduced solar heating and lower evaporation rates contribute to drier conditions. This pattern aligns with the typical global distribution of WV, where the highest concentrations are found in the tropics and lower altitudes, while the lowest concentrations are found in higher latitudes. This result is align with the previous works (Selkirk et al., 2010; Shangguan et al., 2019; Jeffery et al., 2022).

3.3. Seasonal Distributions of water vapor and ozone in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt region

The tropical region of Ethiopia and the subtropical region of Egypt display distinct patterns in the seasonal distributions of water vapor and ozone. These patterns are a result of variations in latitude, atmospheric circulation, temperature, and solar radiation. In Ethiopia, the distribution of water vapor during the spring season (March-April-May) is influenced by atmospheric circulation patterns, topography, and regional weather systems. This includes the transition from the dry season to the rainy season, as depicted in Figure 5 (a). Looking at Figure 5 (a), it is evident that the highest levels of water vapor, ranging from 700 to 850 ppmv, were recorded in April 2012, April 2016, May 2010, and May 2019 during the spring season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. The presence of water vapor in the atmosphere is primarily influenced by factors such as temperature, pressure, and moisture sources like evaporation and transpiration. In Ethiopia, the arrival of spring marks the onset of the rainy season in certain areas, particularly in the southern and southeastern parts of the country. Key factors during this season include increased humidity, water vapor transport, and regional variability. Humidity levels rise as warm air masses move in from the Indian Ocean and the Gulf of Aden. In southern and southeastern Ethiopia, the presence of belg rains is particularly noticeable. The distribution of water vapor in Ethiopia is heavily influenced by the country's topography. The highlands tend to have lower levels of water vapor due to the cooler temperatures at higher elevations. Moist air from the equatorial region, especially from the Indian Ocean, is transported towards the Horn of Africa, leading to an increase in water vapor in the lower atmosphere. During spring, water vapor levels generally rise, especially in the southern and eastern regions of Ethiopia, as a result of the early rainy season and the inflow of moist air from the ocean. In the summer season (Jun-July-August), the distribution of water vapor in Ethiopia is significantly affected by the country's climate systems, as depicted in Figure 5 (b). In Figure 5 (b), it shows that the highest levels of water vapor, ranging from 800 to 1000 ppmv, were recorded in Jun 2019, July 2010, 2011, 2012, 2020, and August 2006, 2010, 2018, 2019, 2020 during the summer season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. The levels of water vapor in Ethiopia are closely linked to the intensity of the monsoon system, temperature, and regional geography. During the summer, the rainy season reaches its peak in most parts of the country, resulting in significant increases in atmospheric water vapor.

The key factors influencing the summer seasons include the monsoon's impact, peak rainfall and humidity, and regional variations in the western and central highlands, as well as eastern and southern Ethiopia. Ethiopia's summer is primarily influenced by the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), which moves northwards, bringing moist winds from the Indian Ocean and the Atlantic Ocean (via the Congo Basin). These winds contribute to higher moisture levels, particularly over the Ethiopian highlands and western lowlands. The summer rains are concentrated in the

central, northern, and western regions of the country. This period sees the highest water vapor levels throughout the country due to heavy rainfall. The western highlands, including areas like Addis Ababa and Gondar, experience intense rainfall, resulting in high water vapor concentrations in these regions. The western and central highlands have the highest concentrations of water vapor due to significant rainfall. The air becomes saturated with moisture during the peak of the rainy season. Eastern and Southern Ethiopia these regions receive less rainfall during the summer, there is still some moisture transported from the Indian Ocean, leading to moderate increases in water vapor, although not as high as in the western highlands.

In autumn (September-October-November (SON)) in Ethiopia, water vapor distributions are influenced by the retreat of the rainy season and a shift in atmospheric circulation patterns. Autumn is a transition period between the main rainy season and the dry season as shown in Figure 5 (c). In Figure 5 (c), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 500 to 700 ppmv were recorded in September 2006, 2020, October 2014 and November 2020 during the Autumn season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. As autumn marks the end of the rainy season, the levels of atmospheric water vapor decrease across much of Ethiopia. However, regional variations occur based on geography and specific climate patterns. In September, the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) begins to shift southward, leading to a weakening of the monsoonal flow that brought moisture into the region during the summer. As a result, the water vapor levels in the atmosphere start to decline, especially in northern, central, and western Ethiopia. From late September onward, most parts of Ethiopia, particularly the northern and central highlands, experience a reduction in humidity and atmospheric moisture. Water vapor levels decrease significantly in these areas as the rains subside. Northern and Central Highlands of Water vapor decreases significantly as the heavy summer rains end, leading to drier air in places like Addis Ababa, Bahir Dar, and Gondar. Southern and Southeastern Ethiopia: In contrast, some parts of southern and southeastern Ethiopia receive light rainfall associated with the small rains during October and November. This leads to slightly higher levels of water vapor in these regions, particularly near the Great Rift Valley and areas bordering Kenya and Somalia. Even after the rains end, there is often residual moisture in the soil, vegetation, and atmosphere, especially in western and southern Ethiopia. This can maintain slightly elevated levels of water vapor into early autumn, though it rapidly diminishes by November. During winter (December-January-February (DJF)) in Ethiopia, the seasonal distributions of water vapor are influenced by the dry season, cooler temperatures, and shifts in atmospheric circulation. Winter is generally characterized by low humidity and a stable atmosphere, with distinct patterns for water vapor. In Figure 5 (d), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 300 to 400 ppmv were recorded in December 2010, January 2006 and February 2020, during the Autumn season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. In winter, Ethiopia experiences one of its driest periods, with significantly reduced water vapor levels across

most of the country. The countrys geographical and climatic diversity, however, leads to some regional differences. Winter is dominated by the northeasterly trade winds, which bring dry and cool air from the Arabian Peninsula and the Horn of Africa. These winds are part of the larger-scale Hadley Cell circulation that affects much of the region. As a result, most of Ethiopia experiences very low levels of water vapor. The absence of significant rainfall, especially in the northern and central highlands, leads to dry atmospheric conditions. Clear skies and reduced evaporation further limit the amount of moisture in the air, causing low water vapor content. Northern and Central Highlands areas like Addis Ababa, Bahir Dar, and Gondar have very low humidity levels during the winter months due to the dry northeasterly winds. The Ethiopian Plateau, known for its higher elevations, also experiences lower temperatures, further reducing the moisture-holding capacity of the atmosphere. Eastern and Southern Lowland regions like the Afar Depression and parts of the Ogaden Desert remain dry, with minimal water vapor due to the arid conditions.

In Ethiopia, the seasonal distribution of ozone during spring (March-April-May (MAM)) is influenced by a combination of atmospheric circulation patterns, topography, and regional weather systems, including the transition from the dry season to the rainy season as shown in Figure 6 (a-d). Near-surface ozone concentrations are influenced by air pollution, including emissions from vehicles, industries, and biomass burning. In rural area of Ethiopia, especially in the highlands, ozone levels tend to be lower due to limited industrial activity. However, regions near urban centers like Addis Ababa might experience localized ozone pollution. In the stratosphere, ozone concentrations are higher and provide a protective layer against ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The distribution of stratospheric ozone in Ethiopia is relatively stable throughout the year, but there is some seasonal variation due to stratospheric circulation patterns, such as the Brewer-Dobson circulation. During spring, this circulation transports ozone-rich air from the tropics towards the poles, but Ethiopia, located near the equator, typically experiences moderate stratospheric ozone levels during this period. Ozone distribution during the summer is influenced by both natural atmospheric circulation patterns and human activities as shown Figure 6 (b). In the summer, tropospheric ozone in Ethiopia may increase slightly in some urban and industrialized regions due to higher temperatures and increased solar radiation, which accelerate photochemical reactions involving pollutants (such as nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds). This is especially the case in larger cities like Addis Ababa, where vehicle emissions and industrial activities contribute to ozone formation. during the summer, the Brewer-Dobson circulation plays a role in transporting ozone from the tropics to higher latitudes. Although Ethiopia is near the equator, this circulation pattern causes slight reductions in stratospheric ozone concentrations as ozone is transported poleward. Ozone levels in autumn are affected by a combination of seasonal weather patterns and regional pollution sources as shown Figure 6 (c). As the rainy season comes to an end and cloud cover decreases, more sunlight reaches the surface. This increases photochemical reactions, leading to a slight rise in tropospheric ozone levels, especially in urban areas such as Addis Ababa. These reactions are driven by emissions

from vehicles and industries, which interact with sunlight to form ozone near the ground. During autumn, the Brewer-Dobson circulation continues to transport ozone from the tropics towards the poles, but since Ethiopia is located near the equator, this has minimal impact on overall stratospheric ozone concentrations. There is typically no significant depletion of the ozone layer in Ethiopia during autumn, and the country remains protected from harmful UV radiation. Overall, Season except summer in Ethiopia shows a notable ozone distribution remains relatively stable with localized variations due to pollution.

In Egypt, the seasonal distribution of water vapor during spring (from March to May) varies across regions but generally reflects the country's desert climate as shown Figure 7 (a). In Figure 7 (a), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 300 ppmv were recorded in March 2011, 2015, April 2010 and May 2010, 2020 during the spring season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. Egypt's geography, including its proximity to the Mediterranean Sea in the north, the Red Sea to the east, and vast arid regions in the interior, influences the distribution of these atmospheric components. Water vapor levels in Egypt during spring are relatively low overall, but they show regional variations depending on proximity to water bodies and prevailing winds. The northern coastal areas, including cities like Alexandria and Port Said, experience higher humidity compared to the interior due to their proximity to the Mediterranean Sea. As spring progresses and temperatures rise, water vapor content in the atmosphere also increases slightly, although it remains moderate. The Nile Delta and Nile Valley, including cities like Cairo and Luxor, experience moderate water vapor levels in spring. The region is relatively dry, but there is a slight increase in atmospheric moisture as temperatures warm up, especially towards May. The vast Western Desert and Eastern Desert regions, which include the Sahara and the Libyan Desert, experience very low water vapor levels in spring. These areas remain arid throughout the season, with minimal moisture in the atmosphere due to the lack of significant water sources. Spring in the desert regions is characterized by dry, hot winds and very low humidity, especially as the Khamsin winds blow from the Sahara Desert. These winds transport hot, dry air across Egypt, further reducing water vapor content in the atmosphere.

In summer (June to August) in Egypt, both water vapor distributions are shaped by the extreme heat and the regional atmospheric circulation patterns as shown Figure 7 (b). The summer season is characterized by intense heat, especially in the interior and southern regions, while the influence of large water bodies such as the Mediterranean Sea and Red Sea plays a role in moderating atmospheric moisture. In Figure 7 (b), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 300 ppmv were recorded in Jun 2020, Jul 2007,2013 and August 2006, 2011, and 2020 during the summer season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. Summer in Egypt is typically hot and dry, with relatively low levels of atmospheric water vapor, particularly in the interior desert regions. However, there are variations depending on proximity to water sources like the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea. The sea breeze brings moisture into the atmosphere, leading to moderate to high humidity levels during

the summer months. This is the most humid part of Egypt during the summer, and the water vapor content increases steadily as the Mediterranean Sea remains warm throughout the season. The Nile Delta and Nile Valley, including Cairo, experience moderate levels of humidity, with a slight increase in atmospheric water vapor compared to spring. The presence of the Nile River provides localized moisture, particularly in areas closer to the riverbanks, but overall, the region remains dry due to the intense heat and arid conditions. Areas along the Red Sea, such as Hurghada and Sharm El-Sheikh, experience moderate to high humidity due to the influence of the Red Sea. The proximity to the sea results in more moisture in the air, especially during summer when the sea temperatures are higher, leading to more evaporation and atmospheric water vapor. The sea breezes from the Red Sea help to cool the coast, bringing moisture inland and increasing humidity along the coastline. However, the water vapor content decreases rapidly as one moves farther away from the coast into the interior deserts. The Western Desert, Libyan Desert, and Eastern Desert remain extremely dry throughout the summer. These vast desert regions experience very low humidity and water vapor levels, as the heat causes rapid evaporation and little moisture is retained in the air. The desert areas, particularly in the southern part of Egypt, experience some of the highest temperatures in the world during the summer, with little to no atmospheric moisture.

During autumn (September to November) in Egypt, the seasonal distribution of water vapor is shaped by the transition from the hot summer to cooler winter conditions as shown Figure 7 (c). Autumn typically brings cooler temperatures, but the country remains largely dry, especially in its interior desert regions. In Figure 7 (c), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 200 to 250 ppmv were recorded in Jun 2020, Jul 2007,2013 and August 2006, 2011, and 2020 during the autumn season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. In autumn, water vapor levels across Egypt are generally decreasing as temperatures begin to cool. The relative humidity and atmospheric moisture levels vary across different regions based on geography and proximity to water bodies. During autumn, the Mediterranean Sea remains warm from the summer heat, which means that sea breezes bring moisture inland, maintaining moderate levels of atmospheric water vapor. As temperatures drop from the summer peak, the evaporation rate decreases, but the proximity to the Mediterranean ensures that humidity remains higher than in inland areas. The Nile Delta and Nile Valley, including Cairo, see gradually declining water vapor levels as the region transitions to cooler weather. Although there is still localized moisture near the Nile River, the overall air becomes drier compared to the summer.

In winter (December to February) in Egypt, the distribution of water vapor and ozone is influenced by cooler temperatures, reduced solar radiation, and shifting atmospheric patterns as shown Figure 7 (d). Egypt's arid climate means that overall humidity levels remain low, but there are regional variations, particularly between coastal areas and the inland desert regions. In Figure 7 (d), we can observe that the maximum water vapor levels ranging from 250

to 350 ppmv were recorded in December 2006, 2016, Jan 2007, 2015 and February 2011 during the autumn season. These measurements were taken within the pressure range of 356 to 200 hPa. During winter, Egypt experiences cooler temperatures and generally lower humidity levels, though proximity to water bodies like the Mediterranean Sea and the Red Sea results in regional variations in atmospheric water vapor. Winter brings rainfall to the coastal areas due to Mediterranean cyclonic systems, and this is the rainiest season for northern Egypt, particularly in December and January. However, rainfall is still low by global standards. The cooler temperatures reduce evaporation, but the sea breezes bring moisture inland, leading to moderate humidity levels along the coast.

Ozone levels in Egypt during spring are influenced by atmospheric dynamics, regional pollution sources, and the presence of sunlight, which drives ozone formation in the lower atmosphere as shown Figure 8 (a-d). tropospheric ozone levels tend to increase during spring due to rising temperatures and longer daylight hours, which promote photochemical reactions involving pollutants such as nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). These pollutants mainly come from traffic, industry, and other human activities. In the stratosphere (the ozone layer), ozone levels remain relatively stable throughout the year, including during spring. The Brewer-Dobson circulation transports ozone from the tropics towards the poles, but since Egypt is located in the subtropics, it experiences moderate to high ozone concentrations in the stratosphere year-round. Egypt is not located near the polar regions where ozone depletion (such as the Antarctic ozone hole) is a major issue. During spring, stratospheric ozone levels remain largely intact over the region, providing effective protection from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation.

Ozone levels during the summer in Egypt are influenced by the combination of strong sunlight, high temperatures, and human activity, particularly in urban areas. There is a clear distinction between tropospheric ozone (ground-level ozone) and stratospheric ozone (ozone layer) as shown Figure 8 (b). In summer, Egypt, especially in urban areas like Cairo, experiences elevated levels of tropospheric ozone. The combination of strong solar radiation and high temperatures accelerates photochemical reactions between pollutants (such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs)) and sunlight. This results in the formation of ground-level ozone, a key component of urban smog. In rural areas and the desert regions of Egypt, the levels of tropospheric ozone are significantly lower due to the lack of industrial pollution and fewer emissions sources. However, the strong sunlight and high temperatures can still lead to some natural ozone formation, although concentrations are much lower than in urban areas. The ozone layer in the stratosphere remains relatively stable throughout the summer. The Brewer-Dobson circulation, which transports ozone from the equator towards the poles, continues to maintain healthy levels of ozone in the stratosphere over Egypt. Egypt does not typically experience significant ozone depletion in the stratosphere during the summer, and the ozone layer continues to provide effective protection from ultraviolet (UV) radiation. However, the intensity of UV radiation is higher during the summer due to the direct overhead position of the sun, even with a stable ozone layer. Ozone levels

in Egypt during autumn show both natural seasonal variations and are influenced by human activity in urban areas as shown Figure 8 (c). The behavior of ozone varies depending on whether it is tropospheric ozone (ground-level) or stratospheric ozone (in the ozone layer). During autumn, the levels of tropospheric ozone in Egypt, especially in urban areas like Cairo, begin to decrease compared to the summer. This is because the lower temperatures and shorter daylight hours reduce the rate of photochemical reactions that produce ozone at ground level. In the stratosphere, ozone levels over Egypt remain stable during autumn. The ozone layer continues to protect the region from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Autumn does not see significant variations in stratospheric ozone levels, as Egypt is far from the polar regions where ozone depletion occurs. Egypt is not affected by ozone depletion events that occur in the polar regions (e.g., the Antarctic ozone hole), so the stratospheric ozone levels remain relatively stable throughout the autumn season, providing consistent UV protection.

Ozone levels in Egypt during winter are shaped by the cooler temperatures, weaker sunlight, and seasonal weather patterns as shown Figure 8 (d). As in other seasons, there is a distinction between tropospheric ozone (ground-level) and stratospheric ozone (ozone layer). In winter, the levels of tropospheric ozone (ground-level ozone) in Egypt are generally lower compared to summer and autumn. This is because the cooler temperatures and reduced sunlight slow down the photochemical reactions responsible for forming ozone at ground level. Without strong sunlight and high temperatures, ozone pollution from vehicle emissions and industrial activities is significantly reduced. The ozone layer in the stratosphere over Egypt remains stable during the winter months. The Brewer-Dobson circulation, which transports ozone from the equator to the poles, continues to maintain healthy levels of ozone in the stratosphere. Egypt, being located in the subtropics, is not directly affected by the seasonal ozone depletion that occurs in the polar regions (such as the Antarctic ozone hole). Therefore, stratospheric ozone levels remain consistent throughout the winter, providing effective protection from UV radiation. Due to the lower angle of the sun in winter, the levels of ultraviolet (UV) radiation reaching the surface are naturally lower, even without significant changes in stratospheric ozone. This means that the risk of UV exposure is reduced during the winter months.

3.4. Saturation mixing ration in the tropical and subtropical region

The tropopause controls the two-way transport of air-mass and minor constituents between the troposphere and the stratosphere. A major mixing process in the UTLS region takes place in the tropical region, where a large number of convective systems and thunderstorms occur. These convective systems can inject water vapour into the lower stratosphere through the tropical tropopause. It is well known that the stratosphere is highly stable, less turbulent and have subsidence nature towards the troposphere. The thematic diagram shown in Figure 9, explains the role of tropopause in exchange and mixing of the air masses between the stratosphere and the troposphere. Figure 9 shows the relation between the tropopause temperature and saturation mixing ratio of water vapour. From the figure, it is clear that

the holding capacity of water vapour which depends upon the saturation mixing ratio increases with air temperature. For example, the water vapour transport from the upper troposphere to the lower stratosphere increases by ~ 1 ppmv with the tropopause temperature changes from 190 K to 192 K. The tropical CPT_h controls the transport of ozone from the stratosphere to the troposphere, and the tropical CPT_t controls the transport of water vapour across the tropopause region.

3.5. Mass flux of ozone and water vapor across the tropopause in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt regions

Our aim is to investigate the mass flux of water vapor and ozone across the tropopause in tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt regions. The maximum mass flux observed in tropical Ethiopia has 3.4 kg/s and 5 kg/s in subtropical Egypt, where as the maximum mass flux of water vapor observed in tropical Ethiopia is 68 kg/s and 30 kg/s in tropical Egypt as shown in Figure 11. The water vapor and Ozone mass flux in the tropopause, which refers to the movement of water vapor from the troposphere to the stratosphere and ozone from stratosphere to troposphere, can vary based on several factors including geographic location, atmospheric conditions, and seasonal variations (Akritidis et al., 2019; Lelieveld et al., 2016; Appenzeller et al., 1996). The regions with more frequent tropopause folds and stronger stratosphere to troposphere exchange (STE) processes tend to have higher water vapor and ozone mass flux. Studies indicates that eastern the eastern mediterranean and middle east, which includes Egypt, are hotspots for the tropopause folds and ozone STE during the summer period (Meul et al., 2018). This suggests that Egypt might experience higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to Ethiopia, which is our results support this one. However, specific data comparing Ethiopia and Egypt directly is limited. The overall patterns suggest that Egypt, being closer to the mediterranean region known for higher tropopause fold activity, might have a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause. Regions closer to like Ethiopia tend to have higher water vapor content in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (UTLS) due to stronger convective activity and higher temperature (Zhang et al., 2024). Ethiopia, being closer to the equator compared to Egypt, is likely to experience more intense convective processes, leading to a higher water vapor mass flux in the tropopause region. this is supported by our study in Figure 11 showing that tropical regions typically have higher water vapor fluxes due to the upward transport of moisture from the troposphere to the stratosphere.

4. Summary and Conclusion

This article examines the transportation of trace gases, including ozone and water vapor, in the upper troposphere to lower stratosphere (UTLS) region from 2006 to 2020. The study utilizes latitude-time and pressure-time data from AURA/MLS satellite to analyze the mass flux of ozone and water vapor crossing the tropopause in tropical and subtropical regions. Overall, except for summer in Ethiopia, the ozone distribution remain relatively stable. Autumn in

Egypt also shows stable ozone levels. However, during winter, the levels of tropospheric ozone in tropical Egypt are generally lower compared to summer and autumn. The transport of ozone from the stratosphere to the troposphere is controlled by the tropical CPT_h, while the tropical CPT_t controls the transport of water vapor across the tropopause. In Ethiopia, the maximum water vapor is observed during summer, while in Egypt it is observed during winter. The annual mean variability of OVMR in Ethiopia ranges from 6–10 ppmv at UTLS, between 50 to 0.001 hPa of pressure. In subtropical Egypt, the range is 6–9 ppmv within the same pressure interval. Similarly, the annual mean variability of WVMR in Ethiopia peaks between 400–600 ppmv at UTLS in the pressure range 200 to 300 hPa during May, June, July, and August. In subtropical Egypt, the peak WVMR value is between 100 to 200 ppmv at UTLS, occurring from March to June within the pressure interval of 300 to 200 hPa. In tropical Ethiopia, SAO is observed in the WVMR, while AO is observed in OVMR. In subtropical Egypt, TAO is observed in WVMR, and AO is observed in OVMR. The maximum mass flux of ozone crossing the tropopause is 5 kg/s in Egypt and 3.4 kg/s in Ethiopia. On the other hand, the maximum mass flux of water vapor crossing the tropopause is 68 kg/s in tropical Ethiopia and 30 kg/s in subtropical Egypt. Our study reveals that Egypt experiences a higher ozone mass flux in the tropopause compared to Ethiopia. Conversely, Ethiopia experiences a higher water vapor mass flux in the tropopause compared to Egypt.

References

- J. R. Holton, P. H. Haynes, M. E. McIntyre, A. R. Douglass, R. B. Rood, L. Pfister, Stratosphere-troposphere exchange, *Reviews of geophysics* 33 (4) (1995) 403–439.
- S. Fueglistaler, A. Dessler, T. Dunkerton, I. Folkins, Q. Fu, P. W. Mote, Tropical tropopause layer, *Reviews of Geophysics* 47 (1).
- G. P. Brasseur, S. Solomon, *Aeronomy of the middle atmosphere: Chemistry and physics of the stratosphere and mesosphere*, vol. 32, Springer Science & Business Media, 2005.
- A. Gettelman, M. I. Hegglin, S.-W. Son, J. Kim, M. Fujiwara, T. Birner, S. Kremser, M. Rex, J. Añel, H. Akiyoshi, et al., Multimodel assessment of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere: Tropics and global trends, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 115 (D3).
- N. Butchart, A. A. Scaife, Removal of chlorofluorocarbons by increased mass exchange between the stratosphere and troposphere in a changing climate, *Nature* 410 (6830) (2001) 799–802.
- A. Brewer, Evidence for a world circulation provided by the measurements of helium and water vapour distribution in the stratosphere, *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 75 (326) (1949) 351–363.
- P. W. Mote, K. H. Rosenlof, M. E. McIntyre, E. S. Carr, J. C. Gille, J. R. Holton, J. S. Kinnersley, H. C. Pumphrey, J. M. Russell III, J. W. Waters, An atmospheric tape recorder: The imprint of tropical tropopause temperatures on stratospheric water vapor, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 101 (D2) (1996) 3989–4006.
- W. Collins, R. Derwent, B. Garnier, C. Johnson, M. Sanderson, D. Stevenson, Effect of stratosphere-troposphere exchange on the future tropospheric ozone trend, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 108 (D12).
- G. M. B. Dobson, Origin and distribution of the polyatomic molecules in the atmosphere, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* 236 (1205) (1956) 187–193.

- T. Corti, B. Luo, M. De Reus, D. Brunner, F. Cairo, M. Mahoney, G. Martucci, R. Matthey, V. Mitev, F. Dos Santos, et al., Unprecedented evidence for deep convection hydrating the tropical stratosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters* 35 (10).
- J. R. Holton, A. Gettelman, Horizontal transport and the dehydration of the stratosphere, *Geophysical Research Letters* 28 (14) (2001) 2799–2802.
- E. Richard, K. Rosenlof, E. Ray, K. Kelly, T. Thompson, M. Mahoney, Upper tropospheric-lower stratospheric in-situ measurements over Hurricane Floyd: The impact of tropical cyclones on stratosphere-troposphere exchange, in: *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, vol. 2001, A51H-09, 2001.
- D. M. Roms, Z. Kuang, Overshooting convection in tropical cyclones, *Geophysical Research Letters* 36 (9).
- I. M. Held, B. J. Soden, Water vapor feedback and global warming, *Annual review of energy and the environment* 25 (1) (2000) 441–475.
- A. Sinha, J. E. Harries, Water vapour and greenhouse trapping: The role of far infrared absorption, *Geophysical Research Letters* 22 (16) (1995) 2147–2150.
- P. M. de F. Forster, K. P. Shine, Stratospheric water vapour changes as a possible contributor to observed stratospheric cooling, *Geophysical research letters* 26 (21) (1999) 3309–3312.
- S. Oltmans, D. Hofmann, Increase in lower-stratospheric water vapour at a mid-latitude Northern Hemisphere site from 1981 to 1994, *Nature* 374 (6518) (1995) 146–149.
- S. Kremser, M. Rex, U. Langematz, M. Dameris, I. Wohltmann, Validation of water vapour transport in the tropical tropopause region in coupled Chemistry Climate Models, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions* 8 (3) (2008) 10999–11037.
- D. F. Hurst, A. Lambert, W. G. Read, S. M. Davis, K. H. Rosenlof, E. G. Hall, A. F. Jordan, S. J. Oltmans, Validation of Aura Microwave Limb Sounder stratospheric water vapor measurements by the NOAA frost point hygrometer, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 119 (3) (2014) 1612–1625.
- A. Lambert, W. Read, N. Livesey, M. Santee, G. Manney, L. Froidevaux, D. Wu, M. Schwartz, H. Pumphrey, C. Jimenez, et al., Validation of the Aura Microwave Limb Sounder middle atmosphere water vapor and nitrous oxide measurements, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 112 (D24).
- O. Cooper, A. Stohl, G. Hübler, E. Hsie, D. Parrish, A. Tuck, G. Kiladis, S. Oltmans, B. Johnson, M. Shapiro, et al., Direct transport of midlatitude stratospheric ozone into the lower troposphere and marine boundary layer of the tropical Pacific Ocean, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 110 (D23).
- C.-H. SHI, B. ZHENG, Y.-J. CHEN, Y. BI, The quasi-biennial oscillation of water vapor in tropic stratosphere, *Chinese Journal of Geophysics* 52 (10) (2009) 2428–2435.
- D. J. Seidel, Q. Fu, W. J. Randel, T. J. Reichler, Widening of the tropical belt in a changing climate, *Nature geoscience* 1 (1) (2008) 21–24.
- D. J. Seidel, W. J. Randel, Variability and trends in the global tropopause estimated from radiosonde data, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 111 (D21).
- T. Birner, Recent widening of the tropical belt from global tropopause statistics: Sensitivities, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 115 (D23).
- T. Davies, E. Schuepbach, Episodes of high ozone concentrations at the earth's surface resulting from transport down from the upper troposphere/lower stratosphere: a review and case studies, *Atmospheric Environment* 28 (1) (1994) 53–68.
- A. Stohl, N. Spichtinger-Rakowsky, P. Bonasoni, H. Feldmann, M. Memmesheimer, H. Scheel, T. Trickl, S. Hübener, W. Ringer, M. Mandl, The influence of stratospheric intrusions on alpine ozone concentrations, *Atmospheric Environment* 34 (9) (2000) 1323–1354.
- R. Vingarzan, A review of surface ozone background levels and trends, *Atmospheric environment* 38 (21) (2004) 3431–3442.
- T. Trickl, H. Feldmann, H.-J. Kanter, H.-E. Scheel, M. Sprenger, A. Stohl, H. Wernli, Forecasted deep stratospheric intrusions over Central Europe: case studies and climatologies, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 10 (2) (2010) 499–524.

- P. Cristofanelli, A. Bracci, M. Sprenger, A. Marinoni, U. Bonafè, F. Calzolari, R. Duchi, P. Laj, J. M. Pichon, F. Roccato, et al., Tropospheric ozone variations at the Nepal Climate Observatory-Pyramid (Himalayas, 5079 m asl) and influence of deep stratospheric intrusion events, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 10 (14) (2010) 6537–6549.
- A. S. Lefohn, H. Wernli, D. Shadwick, S. J. Oltmans, M. Shapiro, Quantifying the importance of stratospheric-tropospheric transport on surface ozone concentrations at high-and low-elevation monitoring sites in the United States, *Atmospheric environment* 62 (2012) 646–656.
- S. Kuang, M. Newchurch, J. Burris, L. Wang, K. Knupp, G. Huang, Stratosphere-to-troposphere transport revealed by ground-based lidar and ozonesonde at a midlatitude site, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 117 (D18).
- M. Lin, A. M. Fiore, O. R. Cooper, L. W. Horowitz, A. O. Langford, H. Levy, B. J. Johnson, V. Naik, S. J. Oltmans, C. J. Senff, Springtime high surface ozone events over the western United States: Quantifying the role of stratospheric intrusions, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 117 (D21).
- H. Wernli, M. Bourqui, A Lagrangian 11-year climatology of (deep) cross-tropopause exchange in the extratropical Northern Hemisphere, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 107 (D2) (2002) ACL–13.
- E. F. Danielsen, Stratospheric-tropospheric exchange based on radioactivity, ozone and potential vorticity, *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences* 25 (3) (1968) 502–518.
- P. Hoor, H. Fischer, L. Lange, J. Lelieveld, D. Brunner, Seasonal variations of a mixing layer in the lowermost stratosphere as identified by the CO-O₃ correlation from in situ measurements, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 107 (D5) (2002) ACL–1.
- A. Zahn, C. Brenninkmeijer, M. Maiss, D. Scharffe, P. Crutzen, M. Hermann, J. Heintzenberg, A. Wiedensohler, H. Güsten, G. Heinrich, et al., Identification of extratropical two-way troposphere-stratosphere mixing based on CARIBIC measurements of O₃, CO, and ultrafine particles, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 105 (D1) (2000) 1527–1535.
- M. Shapiro, Turbulent mixing within tropopause folds as a mechanism for the exchange of chemical constituents between the stratosphere and troposphere, *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences* 37 (5) (1980) 994–1004.
- E. Hints, K. Boering, E. Weinstock, J. Anderson, B. Gary, L. Pfister, B. Daube, S. Wofsy, M. Loewenstein, J. Podolske, et al., Troposphere-to-stratosphere transport in the lowermost stratosphere from measurements of H₂O, CO₂, N₂O and O₃, *Geophysical Research Letters* 25 (14) (1998) 2655–2658.
- S. E. Strahan, A. R. Douglass, Decline in Antarctic ozone depletion and lower stratospheric chlorine determined from Aura Microwave Limb Sounder observations, *Geophysical Research Letters* 45 (1) (2018) 382–390.
- N. P. Gillett, D. W. Thompson, Simulation of recent Southern Hemisphere climate change, *Science* 302 (5643) (2003) 273–275.
- M. P. Baldwin, M. Dameris, T. G. Shepherd, How will the stratosphere affect climate change?, *Science* 316 (5831) (2007) 1576–1577.
- J. Kuttippurath, P. J. Nair, The signs of Antarctic ozone hole recovery, *Scientific reports* 7 (1) (2017) 585.
- S. S. Das, M. Venkat Ratnam, K. Uma, A. Patra, K. Subrahmanyam, I. Girach, K. Suneeth, K. Kumar, G. Ramkumar, Stratospheric intrusion into the troposphere during the tropical cyclone Nilam (2012), *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 142 (698) (2016) 2168–2179.
- P. M. Forster, G. Bodeker, R. Schofield, S. Solomon, D. Thompson, Effects of ozone cooling in the tropical lower stratosphere and upper troposphere, *Geophysical Research Letters* 34 (23).
- L. L. Pan, C. R. Homeyer, S. Honomichl, B. A. Ridley, M. Weisman, M. C. Barth, J. W. Hair, M. A. Fenn, C. Butler, G. S. Diskin, et al., Thunderstorms enhance tropospheric ozone by wrapping and shedding stratospheric air, *Geophysical Research Letters* 41 (22) (2014) 7785–7790.
- D. Akritidis, A. Pozzer, P. Zanis, On the impact of future climate change on tropopause folds and tropospheric ozone, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 19 (22) (2019) 14387–14401.

- J. W. Waters, L. Froidevaux, R. S. Harwood, R. F. Jarnot, H. M. Pickett, W. G. Read, P. H. Siegel, R. E. Cofield, M. J. Filipiak, D. A. Flower, et al., The earth observing system microwave limb sounder (EOS MLS) on the Aura satellite, *IEEE transactions on geoscience and remote sensing* 44 (5) (2006) 1075–1092.
- N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, L. Froidevaux, A. Lambert, G. L. Manney, H. C. Pumphrey, M. L. Santee, M. J. Schwartz, S. Wang, R. E. Cofield, et al., Version 3.3 Level 2 data quality and description document, *JPL D-33509 3 (2)* (2011) 4–1.
- L. Froidevaux, Y. Jiang, A. Lambert, N. Livesey, W. Read, J. Waters, R. Fuller, T. Marcy, P. Popp, R. Gao, et al., Validation of Aura microwave limb sounder HCl measurements, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 113 (D15).
- W. Read, A. Lambert, J. Bacmeister, R. Cofield, L. Christensen, D. Cuddy, W. Daffer, B. Drouin, E. Fetzer, L. Froidevaux, et al., Aura Microwave Limb Sounder upper tropospheric and lower stratospheric H₂O and relative humidity with respect to ice validation, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 112 (D24).
- L. Froidevaux, N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, Y. B. Jiang, C. Jimenez, M. J. Filipiak, M. J. Schwartz, M. L. Santee, H. C. Pumphrey, J. H. Jiang, et al., Early validation analyses of atmospheric profiles from EOS MLS on the Aura satellite, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 44 (5) (2006) 1106–1121.
- J. Ziemke, S. Chandra, G. Labow, P. Bhartia, L. Froidevaux, J. Witte, A global climatology of tropospheric and stratospheric ozone derived from Aura OMI and MLS measurements, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 11 (17) (2011) 9237–9251.
- J. H. Jiang, H. Su, S. Pawson, H.-C. Liu, W. G. Read, J. W. Waters, M. L. Santee, D. L. Wu, M. J. Schwartz, N. J. Livesey, et al., Five year (2004–2009) observations of upper tropospheric water vapor and cloud ice from MLS and comparisons with GEOS-5 analyses, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 115 (D15).
- E. S. Maddy, C. D. Barnett, Vertical resolution estimates in version 5 of AIRS operational retrievals, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 46 (8) (2008) 2375–2384.
- J. Waters, Microwave limb sounding, *Atmospheric remote sensing by microwave radiometry 1* (1993) 383.
- R. F. Jarnot, V. S. Perun, M. J. Schwartz, Radiometric and spectral performance and calibration of the GHz bands of EOS MLS, *IEEE transactions on geoscience and remote sensing* 44 (5) (2006) 1131–1143.
- H. M. Pickett, Microwave limb sounder THz module on Aura, *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 44 (5) (2006) 1122–1130.
- N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, Direct retrieval of line-of-sight atmospheric structure from limb sounding observations, *Geophysical research letters* 27 (6) (2000) 891–894.
- A. Dessler, M. Schoeberl, T. Wang, S. Davis, K. Rosenlof, Stratospheric water vapor feedback, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110 (45) (2013) 18087–18091.
- P. S. Jeffery, K. A. Walker, C. E. Sioris, C. D. Boone, D. Degenstein, G. L. Manney, C. T. McElroy, L. Millán, D. A. Plummer, N. J. Ryan, et al., Water vapour and ozone in the upper troposphere–lower stratosphere: global climatologies from three Canadian limb-viewing instruments, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 22 (22) (2022) 14709–14734.
- H. B. Selkirk, H. Vömel, J. M. Valverde Canossa, L. Pfister, J. A. Diaz, W. Fernández, J. Amador, W. Stolz, G. S. Peng, Detailed structure of the tropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere as revealed by balloon sonde observations of water vapor, ozone, temperature, and winds during the NASA TCSP and TC4 campaigns, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 115 (D10).
- M. Shangguan, W. Wang, S. Jin, Variability of temperature and ozone in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere from multi-satellite observations and reanalysis data, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 19 (10) (2019) 6659–6679.
- J. Lelieveld, S. Gromov, A. Pozzer, D. Taraborrelli, Global tropospheric hydroxyl distribution, budget and reactivity, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 16 (19) (2016) 12477–12493.

- C. Appenzeller, J. R. Holton, K. H. Rosenlof, Seasonal variation of mass transport across the tropopause, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 101 (D10) (1996) 15071–15078.
- S. Meul, U. Langematz, P. Kröger, S. Oberländer-Hayn, P. Jöckel, Future changes in the stratosphere-to-troposphere ozone mass flux and the contribution from climate change and ozone recovery, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 18 (10) (2018) 7721–7738.
- Y. Zhang, Q. Huang, K. Guo, M. Wang, H. Liao, Y. Chou, X. He, Tropopause folds over the Tibetan Plateau and their impact on water vapor in the upper troposphere-lower stratosphere, *Climate Dynamics* 62 (2) (2024) 1423–1437.

Figure 1: Monthly and annual mean of water vapor and ozone variation based on MLS observations from 2006 to 2020 over tropical Ethiopia region

Figure 2: Monthly and annual mean of water vapor and ozone variation based on MLS observations from 2006 to 2020 over subtropical Egypt region

Figure 3: Latitude - pressure diagrams of ozone and water vapor at latitude band of 0 - 20° N and 22 - 40° N (a) Latitudinally water variation in Ethiopia, (b) Latitudinally water variation in Egypt, (c), Latitudinally ozone variation in Ethiopia and (d) Latitudinally ozone variation in Egypt

Figure 4: Latitude - pressure diagrams ozone and water vapor at latitude band of 80 S - 80⁰ N (a) Latitudinal Water vapor variation and (b) Latitudinal ozone variation

Figure 5: Seasonal mean of water vapor distribution at latitude band of 0 - 15⁰ N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Ethiopia region

Figure 6: Seasonal mean of ozone distribution at latitude band of 0 - 15° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in tropical Ethiopia region

Figure 7: Seasonal mean of water vapor distribution at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Egypt region

Figure 8: Seasonal mean of ozone distribution at latitude band of 22 - 35° N (a) Spring, (b) Summer, (c), Autumn and (d) Winter in subtropical Egypt region

Figure 9: Relation between the tropopause temperature and saturation mixing ratio in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt region

Figure 10: Relation between the tropopause temperature and saturation mixing ratio in the tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt region

Figure 11: Mass flux of ozone and water vapor (a) Ozone mass flux in Ethiopia, (b) Water vapor mass flux in Ethiopia, (c), Ozone mass flux in Egypt and (d) Water vapor mass flux in Egypt